

Analysis of the Application of Grammar and Sentence Structure by Native English Speakers in English Talk Show, Sitcom, and Vlog on the YouTube Platform

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ABSTRACT: This study was aimed to evaluate two contrasting perspectives on learning English. The first perspective suggests that learning grammar is not too important to be able to speak English. It argues that since native English speakers do not consciously follow grammar rules, learners should focus on speaking practice instead of worrying about grammar. The second perspective argues that the importance of learning grammar is to construct proper sentences in conversations. It believes that mastering grammar is essential for effectively learning English and that excluding grammar makes learning the language impossible. To evaluate these viewpoints, informal conversations and a monologue by three purposively selected native English speakers from an English Talk Show, Sitcom, and Vlog on YouTube were analysed using a thematic analysis. The data were collected through a combination of non-participant and structured observations. The findings revealed that, contrary to the first perspective, native English speakers consistently use proper grammar, even in informal contexts.

Keywords: *English Talk show, Grammar and Structure Usage, Sitcom, Vlog*

There are a lot of ways and methods of learning a foreign language. However, some of them might be contradictory to each other. For English learners, especially the beginners, this might cause some confusion about which method should best be adopted. For example, one theory recommends that to speak English well, learning grammar is not important while the other would appose to that.

English Tips for You (2024:1), suggests that if we want to succeed in mastering English, we should use the same method we used when learning our native language, Indonesian. How can we do this? We can start by immersing ourselves in English, such as by watching movies, listening to music, engaging in conversations, listening to and observing how people speak, and reading—all in English. As we become accustomed to listening, reading, speaking, and writing in English, we will naturally become familiar with correct grammar structures. Not everyone who is proficient in English holds a degree in English Literature, which means not everyone has

studied grammar in depth. This is because English is not solely about grammar.

However, This opinion seems to be of the opposite to Siregar's (2024:1), who, first of all, questions whether we hear and see people speaking English daily in Indonesia. Certainly not, and that is why we cannot simply learn English through the "speaking" method alone, because we do not hear it every day to understand it well enough to speak it. Consequently, unlike Indonesian language, we cannot learn English unconsciously. We have to study it consciously. And learning consciously is best done through understanding grammar. Vocabulary can follow (using a dictionary).

Nevertheless, Warsono (2022:1) argues that if you study grammar for too long, or if you start learning English with grammar, it will hinder your "speaking skills". Grammar becomes a monitor in your mind that constantly tries to correct what you are about to say. Questions like, "Is this sentence grammatically, correct?" or "Should I use the simple past or past perfect tense in this context?" will keep popping up, preventing you from becoming a fluent speaker. The fact is, you do not need grammar to be a good English speaker. Who studies grammar? Those who need English for academic purposes. Those who are preparing for English proficiency tests that include grammar questions. But for speaking? It is not necessary!

This statement, however, is countered by the EF Blog (2024:1), which argues that grammar is one of the essential components of English that should never be ignored. To have good English skills, you must study grammar. Alongside a strong command of vocabulary and phrases, grammar supports your ability to speak and write in English.

At this point, we see a difference of opinions regarding the importance of learning grammar. But the current question is, do native English speakers themselves actually use good grammar in their everyday conversations? In other words, do the grammar lessons we learn in the classrooms entirely apply to casual dialogues among those whose mother tongue is English? If it

is a situation where formality is required, grammar will undoubtedly be given full attention to avoid mistakes in its use. But we are talking about grammar in everyday conversation. Is its usage 100% aligned with the grammar rules we study in school? To find out about this, Youtube platform has been used to observe the way native speakers of English speak on English Talk Show, Sitcom and Vlog.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Grammar and Structure

Grammar is defined in the Cambridge Dictionary (2024:1) as “the study or use of the rules about how words change their form and combine with other words to make sentences.”. Meanwhile, Ardhini (2023:1) defines grammar as a set of structural rules concerning the syntax of the English language. In other words, grammar is a set of guidelines used to learn a language. With grammar, people can understand how to arrange words into sentences and how to modify word forms according to time indicators and the position of words within a sentence. The rules or formulas discussed in grammar include, for example, tenses, modals, if conditionals, gerunds, etc.

On the other hand, structure, or more precisely language structure, is defined as follows: "The systematic arrangement and organization of words, phrases, and sentences, which enables clear and coherent communication" (StudySmarter, 2024). This means that structure refers to the systematization and organization of words, phrases, and sentences, allowing for clear and consistent communication. In line with this, Nordquist (2019:1) states:

“In English grammar, sentence structure is the arrangement of words, phrases, and clauses in a sentence. The grammatical function or meaning of a sentence is dependent on this structural organization, which is also called syntax or syntactic structure. In traditional grammar, the four basic types of sentence structures are the simple sentence, the compound sentence, the complex sentence, and the compound-complex sentence.”

In other words, in English grammar, sentence structure refers to the arrangement of words, phrases, and clauses within a sentence. The function of grammar or the meaning of a sentence depends on this structural organization, which is also known as syntax or syntactic structure. In

traditional grammar, the four basic types of sentence structures are simple sentences, compound sentences, complex sentences, and compound-complex sentences.

English Talk show

Wikipedia (2024) defines a talk show as follows:

“A talk show (sometimes chat show in British English) is a television programming, radio programming or Podcast genre structured around the act of spontaneous conversation. A talk show is distinguished from other television programs by certain common attributes. In a talk show, one person (or group of people or guests) discusses various topics put forth by a talk show host. This discussion can be in the form of an interview or a simple conversation about important social, political or religious issues and events. The personality of the host shapes the tone and style of the show. A common feature or unwritten rule of talk shows is to be based on “fresh talk”, which is talk that is spontaneous or has the appearance of spontaneity”

Some famous English-language talk shows include *The Oprah Winfrey Show*, *The Ellen DeGeneres Show*, *The Tonight Show*, *Jimmy Kimmel Live!*, *The Late Late Show with James Corden*, *Saturday Night Live*, and others. The choice to analyze talk shows is due to the spontaneity in the interviews or dialogues between the host and the invited guests. This spontaneity means there is no dialogue memorized from a script that has been meticulously edited and refined in terms of grammar. The spontaneity displayed in the conversations indicates how native English speakers genuinely use their language in communication. Here, we can analyze whether their spoken language is well-structured according to the rules of English.

English Sitcom

Unlike English talk shows, English sitcoms are likely to have scripts and scenarios that are pre-written for the actors to memorize for the scenes in the sitcom. Chase (2023:1) defines a sitcom as follows:

“The term “sitcom” is actually a shortened version of “situational comedy.” It refers to a genre of comedy television series that revolves around a fixed set of characters who navigate humorous and often exaggerated situations. Whether as a traditional

American sitcom like Family Matters, an animated sitcom like Family Guy, or a dramedy sitcom like Modern Family, these shows are typically set in common environments like a home, workplace, or a favorite hangout spot. What sets most sitcoms apart is their episodic nature – each episode presents a self-contained story, yet the characters and their relationships grow and evolve over time. It's this unique blend of humor, relatable scenarios, and engaging main characters that give sitcoms their appeal”

So, why was a sitcom included in this research? That was because sitcoms depict humorous and funny situations in everyday life. This means that the language used is everyday English, which is typically far from formal. In this context, we aimed to understand the role of structure/grammar in the dialogues of the characters. Some well-known English-language sitcoms include *Friends*, *The Big Bang Theory*, *Seinfeld*, *The Office* (both the American and British versions), *Modern Family*, *Brooklyn Nine-Nine*, *Two and a Half Men*, *The Simpsons*, *Will & Grace*, and others.

Vlog

A "vlog" is a combination of the words "video" and "blog." The video recordings, usually shared on the internet, are related to someone's activities that are shared with their viewers. These activities can include personal experiences, lifestyle, food, tips and tricks on how to do something, and therefore, are far from formal.

Because of this, a vlog was also included as one of the media for researching the use of grammar when a vlogger communicated with their audience. However, there are some vlogs that use a script in their delivery, and those are not chosen for analysis in this study. The following quote will further explain what is meant by a vlog:

“A vlog is a video documenting the life of a person. As the name suggests, a vlog is a video blog that records the thoughts, opinions, and interests of an individual usually for internet publication and online audience” (SocialBee:2024)

YouTube

It seems that in this internet era, no one is unfamiliar with YouTube. Anyone with a smartphone, especially young people, is likely quite familiar with what is known as YouTube. According to Britannica.com (2024:1):

“YouTube is an American online video sharing platform owned by Google. Accessible worldwide. YouTube launched on February 14, 2005, by Steve Chen, Chad Hurley, and Jawed Karim, three former employees of PayPal. Headquartered in San Bruno, California, United States, it is the second most visited website in the world, after Google Search. YouTube has more than 2.5 billion monthly users, who collectively watch more than one billion hours of videos every day. As of May 2019, videos were being uploaded to the platform at a rate of more than 500 hours of content per minute, and as of 2021, there were approximately 14 billion videos in total”

Due to the phenomenal popularity of YouTube and the fact that access is free, the author chose YouTube to obtain research data. Additionally, YouTube consistently provides subtitles for its videos, which helps avoid errors in text transcription. Unlike television, YouTube allows users to pause, rewind, or skip specific scenes, making it more convenient for detailed analysis. Furthermore, videos on YouTube can be downloaded using applications like TubeMate, which can be installed for free on smartphones.

METHOD

A descriptive research design was used in this study. According to ResearchGuides (2017, p. 1), descriptive research is used to gather information about the current state of phenomena and to describe "what exists" regarding variables or conditions in a situation. The study focused on a single variable: “The Application of Grammar and Sentence Structure by Native English Speakers in English Talk Show, Sitcom, and Vlog on YouTube Platform.” The population of this study included native English speakers who acted as hosts in English talk shows, interviewees, actors in sitcoms, and vloggers who broadcasted their content on YouTube. Due to the large number of individuals in broadcasting and entertainment industry, only one representative from each type of

program was selected, resulting in three sample programs. Each program was estimated to last approximately 3-5 minutes, so the total scenes monitored, recorded, and analyzed amounted to about 10 minutes.

Data collection involved observing each scene and recording every utterance, both phrases and sentences, spoken by the actors in all three programs. Errors were recorded using tally marks if they ever existed. These tally marks were then categorized according to the type of grammar errors made. Percentages were used to determine the majority of grammatical errors by comparing the total number of tally marks in each error classification column.

FINDINGS

The following is a dialogue/interview from a talk show, *The Ellen DeGeneres Show*. Often shortened to "Ellen," this television talk show was hosted by comedian/actress Ellen DeGeneres and had been airing since 2003. The episode cited in this study lasted 6:58 minutes and was entirely in English, as the speakers were native English speakers. The link to watch the episode is: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0OXjCR3Uu0A>

(E: Ellen/the interviewer; J: Justin Bieber)

E: *"Do you have a favorite memory of anything that you did on the show?"*

J: *"I just love the fact that what you do so brilliantly is you create such an amazing atmosphere for me to feel like I can be myself. And I just-- I really appreciate that. Also, I love doing all of the pranks and whatnot. All of those are fun as well. Moments like that to just be silly and just, like I said, be myself, that is a big part of who I am. I'm just a silly person. And you've always accepted me for me. And that's an amazing quality. So, thank you so much."*

The dialogue above contains elements of grammar such as Simple Present Tense, Simple Past Tense, Adjective Clause, Adverb, Noun Clause, Present Participle, Gerund, To Infinitive, Present Perfect Tense, and To Be. The discussion of the use of grammar in this dialogue will be covered in the discussion section.

Meanwhile, "Friends" is an American television sitcom about the lives of six friends living in Manhattan, New York. The show aired from 1994 to 2004 in the United States and had since been broadcast by various television stations in other countries. One of the episodes from this sitcom that will be discussed can be watched at:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s2CHW66yk7U>

S: yeah, so Ross what's your problem?

R: Excuse me?

S: why can't you get a girlfriend your own age?

R: oh it's funny um it's not funny.

S: I don't like you going out with my daughter, Ross.

R: okay, um I can I can say that um but I think if you give me one chance, I can change your mind.

S: okay I'll give you one chance to change my mind. You got one minute... Fine, two minutes, go yeah yeah, a minute and fifty seconds.

R: okay um I want you to know I've never done anything like this before, I mean I mean I've been in um relationships in general but I've never done it with a student I mean I mean I don't, we haven't done it we I mean I mean we've we've done stuff but okay.....

M: how crazy that we'd run into you thank you uh mr...

R: Stevens I'd like you to meet my friends, this is Phoebe Monica and Chandler.

P: so, you're Elizabeth's father huh I can see now where she gets her rugged handsomeness.

M: Is there a mrs. Steven?

C: There's a mr. Bing.

S: No. Unfortunately Lizzie's mom passed away shortly after she was born. I raised her by myself.

M: Oooh....

S: I get that a lot.

R: okay um why don't we all take a seat, you know, and then I'll get us all some some coffee yeah why don't you uh you guys can talk about whatever whatever you want you know whatever pops into your head.

In the dialogue, which is filled with laughter from the studio audience, there are patterns of sentences that fall within the scope of English grammar, including Modals, Present Participles, Conditional Sentence Type 1, To Infinitive, Present Perfect Tense, Past Future Tense, Simple Present Tense, Past Tense, Passive Voice, and Future Tense. The discussion on the appropriateness of these grammatical patterns and the sentences used in the dialogue will be detailed in the discussion section.

Next, the vlog. The following vlog features a vlogger named Abram Engle, who talks about his beloved cat named Kurt. The interesting vlog can be watched at:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=06NRo0I0skc>

Here is an excerpt from the vlogger's monologue:

".....It took Kurt a while to get used to it he was in the bathroom for a while and I had to do the whole process of like keeping him in one space and then slowly introducing him to the whole house and it took him a while which he is chilling now as you can see he's chilling now but it took him a while to get used to it he's just not the greatest at change and so there's a lot of changes coming soon and don't want to just throw another one at him so soon my lease is out for this house and we are moving and another thing is this summer I am getting married so that is another change Hagen my fiance who Kurt is already jealous of and that's going to be a whole another thing of them bonding which is going to be great I know they will end up bonding eventually I mean Hagen she loves Kurt and Kurt sometimes likes her but he's just jealous and yeah they're gonna have to bond but anyway and then if we threw on another cat and he just has another cat like that would just be a lot at once now the time that you've been waiting for when will it happen I don't know exactly when but I would think maybe sometime in the fall or winter when we get settled into a new house....."

The monologue above contains elements of grammar such as Past Tense, Adverb of Manner, Preposition, Gerund, Modal, Present Continuous Tense, Simple Present Tense, To Be, Conditional Sentence Type 2, and Future Tense. The discussion on the appropriateness of grammar rules or usage in the sentences above will be elaborated in the discussion section.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Analysis of the English Talk Show reveals that the use of Past Tense in "...you did on the show" is correct, as it should use Verb 2. Here, Ellen refers to something that happened in the past. The Noun Clause "What you do so brilliantly is..." is correctly formed, where the clause acts as the subject, making 'is' a verb complementing the Noun Clause to complete the sentence. The use of the Adverb of Manner 'brilliantly' is also correct. In other words, Justin distinguishes between 'brilliant' and 'brilliantly,' each serving different functions even though their meanings are similar. The 'To Infinitive' functioning as an Adjective Phrase in "to just be silly and be

myself” appropriately describes the word 'moment,' thus functioning as an adjective or descriptive phrase. The phrase that follows illustrates that the adverb is not just a single word but a collection of words. The Gerund “I love doing all of the pranks” and Present Perfect Tense “you've always accepted me for me” are also in line with grammar rules.

As for the Sitcom “Friends”, Its scripts and grammatical categorization as well as the grammar usage can be seen in the following table:

Table 1
Analysis on Grammatical/Structural Mistakes on Sitcom

No.	Subject	Grammar/ Structure	Sentence/Phrase	Grammatical /Structural Mistakes
1	Modal	Modal+V1	<i>Why <u>can't</u> you <u>get</u> a girlfriend your own age?</i>	None
2	Present Participle as Adjective	V+Ing after noun/pronoun	<i>I don't like <u>you going</u> out with my daughter</i>	None
3	Conditional Sentence Type 1	If+S+V1+(O), S+will/can+V1+(O)	<i><u>if you give</u> me one chance, <u>I can</u> change your mind.</i>	None
4	To Infinitive	S+want+O+To Infinitive	<i><u>I want you to know</u></i>	None
5	Present Perfect Tense	S+have/has+V3	<i><u>I've never done</u> anything like this before</i>	None
6	Past Future Tense	S+would+V1	<i><u>we'd run into you/</u> <u>we would run into you</u></i>	None
7	Simple Present Tense	S+V(s/es)+(O)	<i><u>She gets her rugged handsomeness.</u></i>	None
8	Past Tense	S+V2+(O)+(Adv erb)	<i><u>Lizzie's mom passed away/I raised her</u> by myself.</i>	None
9	Passive Voice	S+ to be +V3	<i><u>She was born</u></i>	None
10	Future Tense	S+Will/shall+V1	<i><u>I'll get us all some some coffee</u></i>	None

The table above shows that the application or use of proper and correct grammar is indeed evident, even in everyday conversations, which are typically informal. The grammar/structure taught in English grammar books is correctly applied in informal dialogues, as seen in the above conversations. However, due to space and time limitations, not all sentences in the dialogues can be discussed individually here. Nevertheless, the author has reviewed all the texts in the dialogue transcripts, and the grammar errors indeed amount to 0% (zero percent).

As for the English Vlog, the explanation can be seen in the following table:

Tabel 2
Analysis on Grammatical/Structural Mistakes on Vlog

No	Subject	Grammar/ Structure	Sentence/Phrase	Grammatical /Structural Mistakes
1	Simple Past Tense	S+V2+(O)+(Adv erb	<i>It took Kurt a while to get used to it</i>	None
2	Adverb of Mannar	Adjective+ly	<i>.....<u>slowly</u> introducing them to the whole house</i>	None
3	Preposition	Certain preposition after adjective	<i>Hagen, my fiance who Kurt is already jealous <u>of</u></i>	None
4	Gerund	V+ing functioning as Noun	<i>.....<u>keeping</u> them in one space and then slowly <u>introducing</u> them to the whole house</i>	None
5	Modal	S+can+V1	<i>You <u>can</u> see</i>	None
6	Present Continuous Tense	S+to be+ Ving(s/es)+(O)	<i>He's <u>chilling</u> now</i>	None
7	Simple Present Tense	S+V(s/es)+(O)	<i><u>She loves</u> Kurt and Kurt sometimes likes her.</i>	None
8	To Be	S+to be+non-verb	<i><u>My lease is out</u> for this house</i>	None
9	Conditional Sentence Type 2	If+S+V2+(O), S+would+V1+(O)	<i><u>if we threw</u> on another cat and he just has another cat like <u>that would</u> just be a lot at once now</i>	None
10	Future Tense	Will+S+V1+(O)?	<i><u>when will it happen?</u></i>	None

In the table above, no discrepancies were found between the grammatical patterns and the sentences used in the monologue. The vlogger spoke spontaneously without memorizing a script, meaning there was no initial effort to check the grammar of what they intended to say, memorize it, before delivering it in front of the camera. This is clearly different from a scripted monologue, where the script would be memorized and rehearsed. The vlogger had determined the topic and main ideas beforehand, but it appears that scripting every word did not occur.

Nevertheless, in this informal setting, all sentences were well-structured and adhered to grammatical rules. No rules were violated. For instance, in the Present Continuous Tense, the vlogger did not forget to place “to be” before the verb-ing, which could happen if one considered grammar unimportant. However, this is exactly how native English speakers speak, with grammatical rules perfectly applied even in informal circumstances.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Native English speakers use their English grammar correctly and accurately, even in casual settings. We might assume that English speakers tend to overlook small details in grammar, such as incorrect use of “to be” or “verb forms” in informal situations. However, after analyzing their casual speech, it is evident that their grammar usage is intact. There is no doubt about it as has been shown by the research data accumulated.

When learning English or any foreign language, it is essential not to be selective. For example, if one only wants to focus on speaking and feels disturbed by learning grammar, it can lead to ineffective language learning. Speaking, Grammar, Reading, Listening, and Writing should be studied with equal enthusiasm and curiosity, as they are closely interconnected and cannot be separated based on personal preferences. Additionally, further research is recommended to understand the use of more complex grammar and its relation to conversations among native English speakers in colloquial language

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